

Volumetric Determination of Molybdenum(VI) and Tungsten(VI) using Aluminium – Copper Alloy as a Reductant

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An aluminium – copper alloy has been used as a reductant in the determination of molybdenum(VI) and tungsten(VI). The process requires 15–20 min and reduction to the lower state is quantitative. The proposed procedure can be used for routine estimations.

Alloys containing 8 and 4% Cu are suitable for reduction of Mo^{VI} and W^{VI}, respectively. Effect of acid strength of the medium and nature of the reduction process are discussed. Mo in ferromolybdenum alloys and W in ferrotungsten alloys can be determined. Interference of commonly occurring ions has been studied. The proposed method has significant advantages over the method using Jone's reductor filled with amalgamated zinc granules.

THE importance of molybdenum and tungsten in the modern perspective lies in their use for increasing the corrosion resistance and tensile strength of steel by alloying with iron. The importance of a volumetric method for the rapid determination of molybdenum and tungsten has long been recognised, but upto the present time no entirely satisfactory method has been suggested. The literature procedures for analysis involve reduction with different metals and metal-amalgams with subsequent oxidimetric finish. The aluminium – copper alloy reductor has been better than others.

Although the reduction of molybdenum¹⁻⁷ and tungsten⁸⁻¹⁴ to their lower oxidation states for the volumetric determination had been a subject of several studies, the use of aluminium metal as a reductor was not explored systematically until the present authors reported the use of aluminium-amalgam for molybdenum(VI)¹⁵. The reductors reported for molybdenum include mercury in 9 M hydrochloric acid^{1,2} and that of bismuth where concentration of hydrochloric acid determines the extent of reduction. Walden *et al.*⁴ used silver as the reductor, which also proved to be unsatisfactory due to poor reproducibility. The analytical studies of tungsten constitute the use of zinc as a reductor^{8,9} which was found unsatisfactory¹⁰ on the reproducibility ground. The improvement in the above method had been suggested by Someya¹¹, who used amalgams of zinc, cadmium and lead at 60°. As yet, the conditions necessary for the application of these methods do not seem to have been defined sufficiently. The aluminium – copper alloy as reductant which has been previously proved useful in the determination of iron(III) and hexacyano-

ferrate(III)¹⁶, is useful in the determination of molybdenum(VI) and tungsten(VI) also.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade and glass-distilled water was used throughout.

The reductor column is a borosilicate glass tube (40 cm × 12 mm i.d. bore) with a stopcock at one end.

The aluminium – copper alloy was prepared by adding aluminium metal to molten copper. The melt was then cast into rods and cut into turnings of 1 mm cross-section. The turnings were analysed for copper¹⁷ and aluminium¹⁸ by standard methods.

Ammonium molybdate (4.600 g) was dissolved in water to give a 250 ml stock solution of Mo^{VI}. It was suitably diluted for further use and standardised by iodometric method¹⁹. Sodium tungstate (1.794 g) was dissolved in water to give a 250 ml stock solution of W^{VI}. It was diluted for further use and standardised gravimetrically by precipitating as barium tungstate²⁰. Ferric alum (21.580 g) was dissolved in about 100 ml water and 1 M H₂SO₄ (10 ml) and was further diluted with water to give a 250 ml stock solution of ferric alum. Potassium dichromate (AnalaR ; 6.120 g) kept in an oven for 2 h at 140°, was dissolved and diluted to 1 dm³ with distilled water to give a 0.021 M solution. For largest recommended Mo/W amounts, it was used as titrant but was suitably diluted for smaller amounts.

Procedure : The column was filled with required acid solution and an aliquot containing 10–200 mg molybdenum(vi) or 10–150 mg tungsten(vi) ion was added taking care that the added solution was in contact with the turnings. After 15–20 min, the solution was drained out from the column in excess ferric alum solution and the washings collected in the same flask. Syrupy phosphoric acid (10 ml) was then added and titrated with standard potassium dichromate solution using sodium diphenylamine as an indicator. The indicator correction was 0.02 ml of potassium dichromate.

Results and Discussion

In all the redox reactions in which metallic reductor is used, the quantitiveness of the reaction depends partly on the properties of the reductant (*viz.* redox potential and surface area), and partly on the properties of the solutions to be reduced such as pH and presence of interfering substance. The standard redox potential of Al^{3+}/Al couple is -1.66 V. If aluminium contains a metal of lower redox potential, its reduction power increases. Hence, we proposed the use of aluminium–copper alloy as the reductant. As copper has low reduction potential than that of aluminium (*viz.* $Cu^{2+}/Cu = +0.337$ V). The reduction power of the alloy ($E^{\circ} = 1.997$ V) is more due to local cell formation with aluminium as an anode and copper as a cathode.

The use of base metals, amalgams and alloys has been reviewed²¹. Alloys containing Zn, Cd, Bi, Pb and Sn are commonly used. Wood's and Rose's metals containing 25% lead are also used²². In all these cases, the reaction with acid was very brisk and gas bubbles hinder the reaction. Combination of two base metals is not advantageous from electrochemical point of view. On this basis Al–Cu is the most suitable combination. Moreover, the alloy is cheap and reaction is fairly smooth.

It was observed that increased acid concentration accelerates the reduction. However, very high acid concentrations are not useful as rapid hydrogen evolution obstructs the reaction. Secondly, in case of tungsten(v), it may be further reduced to tungsten(IV) to some extent. A 1 M sulphuric or perchloric acid was found to be useful for the smooth reduction.

The aluminium–copper alloy reduces molybdenum(vi) to molybdenum(v) and finally to molybdenum(III). Molybdenum blue, an intermediate between molybdenum(vi) and molybdenum(v), is formed in low acid medium, and it passes through a brown coloured $[MoO(H_2O)_2]^{3+}$ species and finally reduces to molybdenum(III) of olive-green colour. In faintly acidic medium, a brown precipitate of $Mo(OH)_3$ is formed during the reduction which may lead to erratic results. The reduction of tungsten(vi) to tungsten(v) by this reductor in low acid concentration is evident from its violet

colour. The results for the determination of molybdenum(vi) and tungsten(vi) in different acid media are given in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

TABLE 1—REDUCTION OF Mo^{VI} IN DIFFERENT ACID MEDIA

MoVI taken = 75 mg, 8% Cu alloy used as reductant,
 $K_2Cr_2O_7$ soln. = 0.12 N

Concn. of acid N	Reduction time min	Amount recovered mg	% Recovery	Std. deviation $n=5$
HCl				
0.05	20	72.13 ± 0.12	96.2	0.07
0.10	15	72.84 ± 0.09	97.1	0.06
0.50	10	73.94 ± 0.24	98.6	0.15
1.00	5			
2.00	5	72.86 ± 0.16	97.1	0.11
HClO₄				
0.10	40	71.87 ± 0.13	95.8	0.10
0.50	20	73.54 ± 0.16	98.0	0.11
1.00	10	74.22 ± 0.13	99.0	0.09
2.00	7	72.60 ± 0.30	96.8	0.25
H₂SO₄				
0.10	30	70.24 ± 0.26	93.6	0.18
0.50	15	72.46 ± 0.14	96.6	0.11
1.00	10	74.48 ± 0.18	99.3	0.13
2.00	7	73.22 ± 0.22	97.6	0.16

TABLE 2—REDUCTION OF W^{VI} IN DIFFERENT ACID MEDIA

W^{VI} taken = 150 mg, 4% Cu alloy used as reductant,
 $K_2Cr_2O_7$ soln. = 0.06 N

Concn. of acid N	Reduction time min	Amount recovered mg	% Recovery	Std. deviation $n=5$
HCl				
0.05	20	141.5 ± 0.5	94.3	0.21
0.10	15	144.7 ± 0.8	96.5	0.40
0.50	10	147.9 ± 0.4	98.6	0.16
1.00	7	147.3 ± 0.5	98.2	0.32
2.00	7	141.8 ± 0.7	94.5	0.52
HClO₄				
0.10	35	144.0 ± 0.8	96.0	0.32
0.50	18	147.3 ± 0.4	98.2	0.18
1.00	10	147.8 ± 0.5	98.5	0.28
2.00	8	147.6 ± 0.8	98.4	0.42

Effect of alloy composition : The time for quantitative reduction increases with the copper content in the alloy as reported earlier¹⁶. For the better efficiency and quantitative results, the reduction of molybdenum(vi) with an alloy containing 8% copper and of tungsten(vi) with an alloy of 4% copper is suggested. Table 3 shows the results related to the choice of the alloy composition.

The presence of commonly occurring ions such as iron(III) and vanadium(v) gives high value due to simultaneous reductions of these metal ions; prior separation of these ions is necessary. The anions, like sulphate, chloride, perchlorate, oxalate and nitrate in small amounts do not interfere. Higher amounts of oxalate interfere with tungsten detection.

TABLE 3—CHOICE OF REDUCING ALLOY MATERIAL

Metal composition	HCl M	Mo ^{VI}		Time for reduction min	%Reco- very
		Taken mg	Found mg		
1% Cu + 99% Al	1.0	150	145.2	4	96.6
4% Cu + 96% Al	1.0	150	148.5	5	98.8
8.3% Cu + 91.7% Al	1.0	150	148.9	7	99.2
15.3% Cu + 84.7% Al	1.0	150	147.0	7	98.0
1% Cu + 99% Al	0.5	150	145.2	4.5	96.8
4% Cu + 96% Al	0.5	150	147.1	5	98.0
8.3% Cu + 91.7% Al	0.5	150	147.8	5	98.5
15.3% Cu + 84.7% Al	0.5	150	146.0	5	97.2

Determination of Mo in ferromolybdenum alloys :

An alloy (BCS No. 231/4) was weighed and dissolved in appropriate quantity of sulphuric acid (1 : 6). Mo was precipitated as its sulphide from an acidic solution. The sulphide precipitate was dissolved in 3 : 10 : 1 mixture of sulphuric, nitric and perchloric acids and boiled. It was then cooled and diluted to the required volume. The analysis was done in duplicate, Mo, Found : 69.8% (std. deviation = 0.23) (certified value, Mo, 70%).

Determination of W in ferrotungsten alloy : An alloy was weighed and fused with sodium carbonate. The fused mixture was extracted with sodium peroxide, boiled for 10 minutes and the filtrate containing sodium tungstate was diluted in a volumetric flask with distilled water. Though the complete separation may not be possible due to formation of a soluble tungstate-iron complex²¹, the extreme low amount of iron does not affect this procedure. The analysis was done in triplicate, W, Found : 70.51% (std. deviation = 0.18) (certified value, W, 71.2%).

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